

S Fig. 12. Forest plot displaying the TSMR analysis results for the effect of ANDs on EBV antibodies. The analysis was conducted using TSMR, with a Bonferroni-corrected significance threshold set at $P = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$

S Fig. 13 MR estimate results of MS on Anti-EBV IgG seropositivity.

S Fig. 14 MR estimate results of MS on EBV EA-D antibody levels.

S Fig. 15 MR estimate results of MS on EBV EBNA-1 antibody levels.

S Fig. 16 MR estimate results of MS on EBV VCA p18 antibody levels.

S Fig. 17 MR estimate results of MS on EBV ZEBRA antibody levels.

S Fig. 18 MR estimate results of NMO on Anti-EBV IgG seropositivity.

S Fig. 19 MR estimate results of NMO on EBV EA-D antibody levels.

S Fig. 20 MR estimate results of NMO on EBV EBNA-1 antibody levels.

S Fig. 21 MR estimate results of NMO on EBV VCA p18 antibody levels.

S Fig. 22 MR estimate results of NMO on EBV ZEBRA antibody levels.